

Spectral and physicochemical studies of Ni^{II} complexes with some nitrogen-oxygen and nitrogen-sulphur donor ligands

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Manuscript received 30 August 2006, accepted 3 November 2006

Abstract : Ni^{II} complexes are synthesized with thiosemicarbazones (L¹, L³ and L⁵) and semicarbazones (L², L⁴ and L⁶) derived from pyrrole-2-carboxyaldehyde, 2-acetyl furan and 2-acetyl thiophene. These complexes are characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility measurements, mass, IR, electronic and EPR spectral studies. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes in DMSO corresponds to non electrolyte for all the complexes except [Ni(L¹)₂](NO₃)₂, [Ni(L³)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Ni(L⁴)₂](NO₃)₂ which are 1 : 2 electrolyte. On the basis of spectral studies an octahedral geometry may be assigned for all the complexes except [Ni(L¹)₂](NO₃)₂, [Ni(L³)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Ni(L⁴)₂](NO₃)₂ which are of tetrahedral geometry.

Keywords : Spectral studies, nickel(II) complexes, thiosemicarbazone, carbazone.

Thiosemicarbazones usually act as chelating ligands with transition metal ion, bonding through the sulphur and hydrazinic nitrogen atom. Thiosemicarbazones and their complexes have received considerable attention because of their pharmacological activities¹.

In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Ni^{II} complexes with thiosemicarbazones (L¹, L³ and L⁵) and semicarbazones (L², L⁴ and L⁶) derived from pyrrole-2-carboxyaldehyde, 2-acetyl furan and 2-acetyl thiophene.

Structure of ligands

- X = NH, R = H, Y = S, for L¹;
- X = NH, R = H, Y = O, for L²;
- X = O, R = CH₃, Y = S, for L³;
- X = O, R = CH₃, Y = O, for L⁴;
- X = S, R = CH₃, Y = S for L⁵;
- X = S, R = CH₃, Y = O, for L⁶

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and procured from Sigma Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. Ligands L¹, L², L³, L⁴, L⁵ and L⁶ were prepared and the methods of their preparation are given below.

Preparation of ligands L¹, L³ and L⁵ : Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding carbonyl compound (ketone/aldehyde) (0.01 mol) was mixed with hot ethanolic solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.95 g, 0.01 mol). The mixture was refluxed for about 2–3 h on a water bath. On cooling the contents the precipitate were separated out in each case. The same was filtered, washed with 50% aqueous ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Preparation of ligands L², L⁴ and L⁶ : An aqueous solution (20 mL) of semicarbazone HCl (1.11 g, 0.01 mol) was added to an ethanolic solution (20 mL) of corresponding ketone (0.01 mol) in the presence of sodium acetate (1.36 g, 0.01 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously for an hour. The crystalline product which formed was collected by filtration in each case, washed several times with hot water and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀.

Synthesis of complexes :

Hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of nickel chloride/nitrate salts (0.005 mol for each case) was mixed with

Table 1. Analytical data of ligands

Ligands	M.W.	Color	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :		
					Found/(Calcd.)		
					C	H	N
L ¹	168	White	153–155	72	43.0 (42.8)	4.6 (4.8)	33.5 (33.3)
C ₆ H ₈ N ₄ S							
L ²	152	White	203–206	78	47.6 (47.3)	5.0 (5.3)	36.9 (36.8)
C ₆ H ₈ N ₄ O							
L ³	183	Dark yellow	108–110	75	46.1 (45.9)	5.1 (4.9)	21.8 (22.0)
C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ OS							
L ⁴	167	Light yellow	160–162	74	50.4 (50.3)	5.8 (5.4)	25.3 (25.1)
C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂							
L ⁵	199	White	159–161	70	42.4 (42.1)	4.8 (4.5)	21.4 (21.1)
C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂							
L ⁶	183	Light yellow	195–197	73	46.0 (45.8)	4.7 (4.9)	22.6 (22.9)
C ₇ H ₉ N ₃ OS							

hot ethanolic solution of the respective ligand (0.01 mol) and refluxed for 3–4 h on a water bath. On cooling the contents, the colored complex separated out in each case. The same was filtered, washed with 50% aqueous ethanol and dried in vacuum over P₄O₁₀. Purity of the complexes was checked by TLC.

Physical measurement :

The C, H, N were analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. Molar conductance was measured on the Elico (CM82T) conducting bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature on a Gouy balance using CuSO₄·5H₂O as a calibrant. Mass spectra were recorded on JEOL, JMS.DX-303 mass spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer.

Results and discussion

Ligands L¹, L³ and L⁵ : The IR spectra of ligands show bands around 3380 and 3171 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to -NH₂ and -NH groups respectively. The bands due to ν(C=S) and ν(C=N) groups appeared around at 1107 and 1597 cm⁻¹. The mass spectrum of free ligands L¹, L³ and L⁵ confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak at 169, 184 and 200 amu respectively corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺ + 1). It also shows a peak corresponding to loss of (-CSNH₂) and various other fragments.

Ligands L², L⁴ and L⁶ : The IR spectra of ligands show bands around at 3380 and 3171 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to -NH₂ and -NH group respectively. The band ν(C=N) appeared around at 1601 cm⁻¹. The mass spectrum of free ligands L², L⁴ and L⁶ confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak at 153, 168 and 184 amu respectively corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺ + 1). It also shows a peak corresponding to loss of (-CONH₂) and various other fragments. The mass spectra of complexes confirm the proposed formula by showing a peak corresponding to the molecular ion (M⁺ + 1).

Complexes : On complexation the bands corresponding to ν(C=N) and ν(C=S) (in case of thiosemicarbazone) shifted towards lower side (around ca. 20–30 cm⁻¹) suggests that the ligand acts as bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of ν(C=N) group and sulphur of ν(C=S) group. In case semicarbazone the bands of ν(C=N) and ν(C=O) shifted towards lower side (around ca. 20–30 cm⁻¹) suggests that the ligand also acts as bidentate chelating agent coordinating through nitrogen of ν(C=N) group and oxygen of ν(C=O) group.

On the basis of elemental analysis the complexes were found to have the composition as shown in Table 2. The molar conductance measurements of all the complexes in

Table 2. Elemental analysis and molar conductance data of complexes

Complex	M.W.	Mol. cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Color	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
						Found/(Calcd.)			
						Ni	C	H	N
Ni(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂	465.71	14	Bluish brown	200	60	12.43 (12.60)	30.70 (30.92)	3.60 (3.43)	24.28 (24.04)
Ni(L ¹) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	518.71	150	Dark green	205	62	11.55 (11.31)	27.59 (27.76)	3.29 (3.08)	26.73 (26.99)
Ni(L ²) ₂ Cl ₂	433.71	12	Brown	245	62	13.31 (13.53)	33.53 (33.20)	3.42 (3.68)	25.58 (25.82)
Ni(L ²) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	486.71	14	Light green	238	61	12.28 (12.06)	29.34 (29.58)	3.03 (3.28)	28.53 (28.76)

Table-2 (contd.)

Ni(L ³) ₂ Cl ₂	495.71	21	Green	140	58	11.61 (11.84)	33.64 (33.89)	3.40 (3.63)	16.17 (16.94)
Ni(L ³) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	548.71	140	Greenish blue	143	63	10.44 (10.69)	30.40 (30.61)	3.53 (3.28)	20.67 (20.41)
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ Cl ₂	463.71	17	Buff green	197	61	10.79 (12.66)	36.47 (36.22)	3.64 (3.88)	18.33 (18.11)
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	516.71	152	Brown	192	59	11.59 (11.36)	32.25 (32.51)	3.70 (3.48)	21.45 (21.67)
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ Cl ₂	527.71	10	Dark green	187	65	11.36 (11.12)	40.70 (40.93)	3.64 (3.48)	15.67 (15.91)
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	580.71	15	Light green	185	67	10.36 (10.11)	37.33 (37.19)	3.34 (3.09)	19.50 (19.28)
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ Cl ₂	495.71	12	Cream yellow	220	57	11.63 (11.84)	33.58 (33.80)	3.26 (3.02)	16.71 (16.94)
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	548.71	16	Brown	232	62	10.48 (10.69)	30.42 (30.60)	3.02 (3.28)	20.64 (20.41)

DMSO correspond to non electrolytic nature² except [Ni(L¹)₂](NO₃)₂, [Ni(L³)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Ni(L⁴)₂](NO₃)₂ complexes which are 1 : 2 electrolyte. Thus the complexes may be formulated as [Ni(L)₂X₂] where [L = L¹, L², L³, L⁴, L⁵ and L⁶] and X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ except [Ni(L¹)₂](NO₃)₂, [Ni(L³)₂](NO₃)₂ and [Ni(L⁴)₂](NO₃)₂.

IR spectra of [Ni(L¹)₂](NO₃), [Ni(L³)₂](NO₃) and [Ni(L⁴)₂](NO₃) complexes show sharp and strong band at 1384 cm⁻¹ indicate that the nitrate group is uncoordinated. IR spectra of nitrate complexes with ligands L², L⁵ and L⁶ display three absorption bands around at 1415–1440, 1290–1320 and 1020–1050 cm⁻¹ suggesting that both the nitrate groups are coordinated to the metal ion³.

Nickel(II) complexes : The value of magnetic moments for the complexes under study lies in the range from 2.92–3.98 B.M.⁴ (Table 3). Electronic spectra of the chloro and nitrate complexes (except nitrate complexes with ligands L¹, L³ and L⁴) show electronic spectral bands in the range 8580–13000, 11000–20000 and 19000–27000 cm⁻¹. These electronic spectral bands may be assigned to the spin allowed transitions ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{2g}, ³A_{2g} (F) → ³T_{1g} (F), ³A_{2g} (P) → ³T_{1g} (P) corresponding to an octahedral geometry^{3,5}. The nitrate complexes of Ni^{II} with ligands L¹, L³ and L⁴ have medium intensity electronic spectral band around at 9000 cm⁻¹ assigned as ν₁. The band at 10000–16500 cm⁻¹ corresponds to ν₂ and it is not split, as the excited state is orbitally non-degenerates.

Table 3. Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data of complexes

Complex	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Electronic spectral data (cm ⁻¹)		
		ν ₁	ν ₂	ν ₃
Ni(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂	2.92	9620	14560	25060
Ni(L ¹) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.95	7900	14640	24000
Ni(L ²) ₂ Cl ₂	3.01	9770	15250	24600
Ni(L ²) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	3.98	9620	14525	24000
Ni(L ³) ₂ Cl ₂	2.97	9600	14125	24750
Ni(L ³) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.94	8580	16500	24600
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ Cl ₂	3.04	9750	15300	24975
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	3.02	8660	13950	21575
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ Cl ₂	2.97	9680	16200	24500
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.93	9650	15250	24600
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ Cl ₂	3.04	9790	14925	24790
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	2.97	7800	13650	24650

The ν₃ transition appears at 14000–25000 cm⁻¹ indicates tetrahedral geometry.

Ligand field parameters :

Various ligand field parameters are calculated for the complexes. The Nephelauxetic parameter β was readily obtained by using the relation β = B (complex)/B (free ion), where B free ion for Ni^{II} is 1041 cm⁻¹⁶. The value of β lies in the range 0.61–0.95 (Table 4). These values indicate the appreciable covalent character of metal ligand σ bond.

Table 4. Ligand field parameters of complexes

Complex	LFSE (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Dq (cm ⁻¹)	β
Ni(L ¹) ₂ Cl ₂	137	962	0.68
Ni(L ¹) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	113	790	0.95
Ni(L ²) ₂ Cl ₂	140	977	0.67
Ni(L ²) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	137	962	0.61
Ni(L ³) ₂ Cl ₂	137	960	0.64
Ni(L ³) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	108	758	0.78
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ Cl ₂	139	975	0.70
Ni(L ⁴) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	110	766	0.80
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ Cl ₂	139	968	0.74
Ni(L ⁵) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	138	965	0.69
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ Cl ₂	140	979	0.66
Ni(L ⁶) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂	112	780	0.95

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to DRDO, New Delhi for financial assistance, IIT Bombay for recording EPR spectra. We are also thankful to ACBR, USIC, Delhi University for recording IR and mass spectra.

References

1. N. K. Singh and A. Srivastava, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2000, **25**, 133.
2. W. G. Geary, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
3. C. R. K. Rao and P. S. Zacharias, *Polyhedron*, 1977, **12**, 1201; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochimica Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 3079; M. Shakir, S. P. Varkey and P. S. Hameed, *Polyhedron*, 1993, **12**, 2775; S. Chandra and L. K. Gupta, *Spectrochimica Acta (A)*, 2004, **60**, 2767; M. Shakir, O. S. M. Nasman, A. K. Mohamed and S. P. Varkey, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1996, **710**; K. Nakamoto, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Coordination Compounds", Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970.
4. B. N. Figgis, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Vol. 267, Interscience, New York, 1966.
5. A. B. P. Lever, "Crystal Field Spectra, Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, 249; F. Athar, F. Arjmand and S. Tabassum, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 426.
6. R. R. Fenton, R. Gauci, P. C. Junk, L. F. Lindoy, R. C. Luckay, G. V. Meehan, J. R. Price, P. Turner and G. Wei, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 2185; C. C. Silviacarvalho, R. Delgado, M. G. V. Drew, V. Felix and B. J. Goodfellow, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2003, 3172; S. Chandra, L. K. Gupta and K. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 833.